

CREATIVITY AS A CATALYST FOR EMPOWERING NIGERIAN GRADUATES AND ADVANCING THE NATION

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Education remains a fundamental driver of national development, human capital formation, and socioeconomic transformation in modern societies. It serves as a vehicle for transmitting knowledge, values, skills, and cultural heritage, while empowering individuals to realize their creative potential and engage productively in economic and civic life. In Nigeria, a country endowed with abundant natural and human resources, education has the potential to foster innovation, entrepreneurship, and sustainable development. However, persistent structural inefficiencies, outdated policies, and implementation challenges continue to limit the capacity of the Nigerian education system to fully harness the talents and creativity of its graduates. This paper examines the role of education in equipping graduates with skills necessary for national advancement, highlighting the need for systemic reforms, strategic investment, and innovative approaches to curriculum and pedagogy. By strengthening the link between education and creativity, Nigeria can enhance graduate employability, stimulate economic growth, and achieve long-term national development objectives.</p>	<p>Education, Graduate empowerment, Creativity, National development, Human capital</p>

Introduction

In modern societies, education is a critical determinant of national development, human capital formation, and socioeconomic transformation. It is a universally acknowledged catalyst for personal and collective advancement. Through education, societies transmit knowledge, values, skills, and cultural heritage across generations. It empowers individuals to maximize their creative potential and equips them with competencies for productive engagement in economic and civic life. For a country like Nigeria, which is richly endowed with both natural and human resources, education should ideally serve as a robust foundation for innovation, entrepreneurship, and sustainable development. However, decades after independence, the Nigerian education system is still grappling with structural inefficiencies, outdated policies, and implementation failures that have hampered its capacity to unleash the full creative and productive potential of its graduates.

The debate around education and its utility for nation-building in Nigeria is intricately linked with governance—defined broadly as the processes, institutions, and actors that make and implement public policy. At the heart of

governance is the responsibility of the political leadership to formulate policies that are not only well-intentioned but effectively executed. In the context of education, this means ensuring that policies go beyond paper commitments to become practical instruments that align educational outcomes with national needs, especially in a country that boasts significant economic and demographic advantages. Unfortunately, the lived reality in Nigeria paints a contrasting picture. High unemployment rates, widespread underemployment, and the rise of socio-economic vices such as banditry, cybercrime, and kidnapping are often traced to a failure of the education system to adequately equip graduates with the creative skills and self-reliant mindset necessary for navigating contemporary challenges.

Nigeria's development narrative is paradoxical. On one hand, the country is richly blessed with vast arable land, abundant mineral deposits, and a youthful population with tremendous potential. On the other hand, it remains ensnared in a cycle of poverty, dependency, and economic underperformance. Scholars such as Rodney (1976) and Fejokwu (1996) have observed that economic development is not merely a function of natural resource availability but depends significantly on the capacity of a people to utilize such resources innovatively. Rodney, in particular, emphasized that a society develops economically as its members collectively enhance their ability to deal with the environment—a process that depends on science, technology, and organized labor, all of which are anchored on education. By implication, education must not only be theoretical but also practical, experimental, and technology-driven to produce a workforce capable of turning resources into wealth and transforming challenges into opportunities.

Despite the promises contained in various iterations of the National Policy on Education (NPE), particularly the 2008 edition which stresses the need for activity-based and ICT-supported learning, the gap between policy and practice remains glaring. Tertiary institutions, in particular, continue to churn out graduates who are ill-equipped for the labor market and who often lack the entrepreneurial orientation required to create employment for themselves and others. This dissonance has triggered widespread disillusionment among the youth and has fueled a preference for white-collar jobs, despite their increasing scarcity. The disconnection between what is taught in schools and what is required in real-life settings also explains the low levels of innovation, patent development, and scalable startup creation among Nigerian graduates.

Education is supposed to be the bedrock of societal transformation. However, when educational institutions become mere degree mills—focusing on rote learning, theoretical knowledge, and outdated syllabi—the result is a workforce that lacks adaptability, problem-solving capacity, and creativity. This is evident in the employability crisis that Nigeria currently faces. Many employers complain about the inability of graduates to meet basic job requirements. Graduates, on the other hand, lament the lack of opportunities, even when they are willing to explore entrepreneurial avenues. The underlying cause in many cases is not a lack of interest or motivation, but rather the absence of practical training, mentorship, and systemic support to nurture entrepreneurial ambition.

In essence, the problem of graduate unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria is not solely a consequence of economic decline or job market saturation. It is fundamentally rooted in governance failures in the education sector. These include inadequate investment in infrastructure, poor curriculum design, insufficient training of educators, lack of industry-academia linkages, and widespread corruption in the management of educational institutions. All of these have collectively eroded the capacity of the education system to function as a tool for empowerment and innovation. For instance, laboratories in many public tertiary institutions are either ill-equipped or completely non-functional, making it impossible for students in the sciences and engineering fields to acquire

hands-on experience. Similarly, entrepreneurship programs, where they exist, are often poorly funded and delivered as optional courses rather than integral components of the academic program.

The implications of these challenges are far-reaching. First, they contribute to the growing brain drain, as many young Nigerians seek better educational and professional opportunities abroad. Second, they perpetuate cycles of dependency and poverty, as graduates without skills or opportunities become liabilities rather than assets to the economy. Third, they foster social unrest, as unemployed and frustrated youths become vulnerable to manipulation by political actors or turn to crime as a means of survival. Lastly, the failure to harness the creative potential of the youth population means that Nigeria is missing out on the demographic dividend that has propelled other nations to prosperity.

Yet, the situation is not irredeemable. Nigeria still has a window of opportunity to recalibrate its education system in line with global best practices. To achieve this, governance reforms must be prioritized. These should include improved funding of education, transparent and accountable policy implementation, periodic curriculum review to reflect industry needs, and strategic partnerships with the private sector. Furthermore, teaching and learning should be driven by technology, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Skills such as critical thinking, digital literacy, design thinking, and project-based learning must be embedded into academic programs from the foundational level to the university. Graduate entrepreneurship should also be encouraged through mentorship, incubation programs, and targeted funding schemes that empower youth to translate ideas into viable business ventures.

In doing so, government must also play a more facilitative role in job creation—not necessarily by employing every graduate, but by creating an enabling environment where small and medium enterprises can thrive. This includes reducing bureaucratic bottlenecks, offering tax incentives, providing seed capital, and ensuring access to markets. In addition, education regulatory agencies such as the National Universities Commission (NUC), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), and Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) must enhance their oversight functions to ensure that institutions uphold minimum standards in pedagogy, content delivery, and graduate output.

Another important dimension is the need for values reorientation. Education should not only aim at cognitive development but also at character formation. Nigerian graduates must be taught the values of hard work, discipline, creativity, and integrity. These are essential virtues for any society that seeks sustainable development. Equally, there must be deliberate efforts to integrate indigenous knowledge systems and local content into the curriculum so that students can relate their education to their immediate environment and societal needs. This will promote relevance, identity, and motivation among learners, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes and creativity.

In conclusion, the challenges facing Nigerian graduates in terms of creativity, job creation, and self-reliance are not isolated problems. They are systemic issues rooted in governance failures, policy-practice gaps, and institutional weaknesses. Addressing them requires a holistic approach that combines educational reform, governance restructuring, economic re-engineering, and social transformation. Only then can the country harness the full potential of its youth population and achieve the vision of inclusive and sustainable development.

Literature Review

The Concept of Creative Potential

It is pertinent to realize that nature has not only provided man with natural resources but also, the creative potential and skills for tapping, processing and utilization of the end products for human survival and comfort. Therefore, the role of education in the development of creative potential/skills cannot be overemphasized. Thus, the term

creativity has to do with man's ability to create or the quality of being creative. Besancon, Lubart and Harbor, (2013) assert that "creativity is increasingly recognized as a valuable asset for individuals in their daily problem solving and their professional careers, that contributes to personal and societal development". Without doubt, unemployment, joblessness, robbery and different forms of social vices and insecurity, characterize the Nigerian state today. In the context of peace and national development, and with particular reference to abundant human and material resources in Nigeria therefore, creativity is required by Nigerians to drive national development and as a remedy to social problems, through the application of knowledge and skills which are products of not just qualitative education, but creativity-driven kind of education. Thus, creative potential is a latent ability to produce original as well as adaptive work, which is a function of an individual's training or education (Walberg, 1988). Besancon et al, (2013) differentiate creative potential from intellectual ability when they posit that whereas intellectual ability often results in academic success, creative potential is best accomplished in original and unique outputs, recognized as valuable in a domain-based context. Therefore, creative achievement refers to actual production of a creative output that has been recognized as creative by certain group of persons. Agba and Ushie, (2014 p 187) have pointed out that "Information and Communication Technology have reduced the employment of highly educated workers in most organizations since their jobs are replaced by sophisticated information processing machines." Teaching and learning in Nigeria should therefore promote indigenous knowledge (IK) to enhance productivity. Nakashima and Rove, (2002) define indigenous knowledge as "the incomplete arrays of knowledge, know-how, practices and representations that guide human societies in their innumerable interactions with natural milieu; ...fishing and gathering, struggles against disease and injury; naming and explaining natural phenomena, and strategies for coping and changing environments".

Apparently therefore, promoting indigenous knowledge in teaching and learning in Nigerian educational system is fundamental to job creation, employability, self reliance and national development. As Agba and Ushie (2014 p 75) have rightly stated, "it is the knowledge that enables members of a given society to carry out their economic, social and industrial activities effectively" thereby contributing in job creation, employment and national development.

Education and Development of Creative Potential

As earlier established, there is a linkage between quality education, creative potential/skills development, resources utilization and national development or nation building. In the light of this, the National Teachers' Institute, Kaduna (2016) defines education as the process of developing knowledge and ability in learners for personal and societal enhancement. It is clear from the foregoing definition that education involves teaching and learning (teacher and learner). Thus, developing learners' creativity in educational setting is a complex endeavour. First, it requires that the nature of the concept of creativity be consensually understood by psychologists, educators, teachers and the scientific community. Second, it supposes that the instruments measuring accurately this concept in learners be available. Third, interpretations made from creative scores should lead to informed decision in terms of orientation, and accurate implementation of creativity learning in the classroom (Besancon, Lubart and Harbor, 2013).

Advantages of Creative Potentials Development

1. Job creation
2. Low rate of unemployment
3. Increase in production of goods and services
4. Enhanced standard of living

5. Increase in Gross Domestic Products GDP
6. Maximum utilization of economic/available resources
7. Increase in per capita income
8. Export of surplus products
9. Economic growth and development.
10. Reduced crime rate
11. Economic diversification
12. Invention/creation of appropriate/relevant technology with direct impact on both social and physical environment.

Theoretical Framework

The framework of analysis for this study is the Human Capital Theory. This theory presupposes that education and training are investments that make people genuinely productive. "The first use of human capital as a term in modern economic literature was by Theodore Schultz who classified expenditures on human capital as investment rather than consumption" (Adiele and Ibietan, 2017 p. 8). Adam Smith, Gary Becker and Nobel Laureate are some of the advocates of this theory. The theory sees human capital as knowledge, skills, attitudes, aptitude and other traits that contribute to production (Goode in Fleischhaver, 2007 p. 4). This suggests that, the knowledge and skills acquired by the citizens through education and training is a form of capital which is a product of deliberate investment that yields return in the form of employment, job creation and income earnings which further culminate in self reliance and better standard of living.

Thus, when Nigerian government gives priority attention to education by not only formulating education policies but also, ensuring that the policies are efficiently and effectively implemented, by providing both the human, material and financial resources needed for skills and knowledge acquisition in institutions of learning, the creative potentials of Nigerian graduates will definitely be enhanced. This will not only guarantee employable graduates but also, a number of them will be able to create jobs by themselves for income earnings and self reliance. In this context therefore, human capital development should not be theoretical or a mere paper work but practical in a manner that teaching and learning in institutions of higher learning should be practical, activity based, experimental and ICT supported. Hence, the economic benefit of investing in education and training the individuals can be measured by the net gain in lifetime earnings accruing as a result of their investment in education and training. As Pahos and Galanaki, (2018) "remarked that job performance is an achievement that is both practical and measurable" (Imucheri and Kakub, 2022 p. 67). Consequently, policy makers tend to accept the premise that investment in education and training is not only a good thing, but a means of securing higher economic growth and national prosperity (Wobmann, 2008).

Natural Resources in Nigeria and their Economic uses

As earlier established, Nigeria is a resource-rich country. It is the world's largest producer of columbite, a mineral containing iron, magnesium, and niobium. Other natural resources include limestone, gypsum, granite, copper, zinc, gold and petroleum resources (crude oil). About 80 percent of Nigeria's land is suitable for farming and grazing. The variety of crops includes cocoa, cassava, yams, rice, maize, grandnut, millet, sorghum, plantains, amongst others. Goats are the leading livestock, followed by sheep and cattle. Despite these resources however,

the mainstay of the economy since the 1970s has been petroleum (Fejokwu, 1996, Britannica, 2010). Akpan-Idiok, (2012) has identified some mineral resources and their uses in Nigeria with large reserves.

1. Tin: used for making cans, roofing sheets, petrol tanks, utensils and ornaments, tin foil as wrapping materials
2. Columbite: for manufacturing of heat resisting and chemical resisting steel in gas turbine and jet engine for aircraft.
3. Tantalite: because of its resistance to acid corrosion, it is used in chemical equipment, in surgery for skull plate, in tool steel.
4. Wolframite: for hardening metal in high speed tool steel, valves, springs, chisels, files.
5. Iron-ore: for production of iron and steel for mechanical, constructional, electrical industries; for ship building, making of rails, automobiles, aircrafts, bridges
6. Lead and Zinc: used for soldering, bearings, lead foils, ammunition and ornamental sting, plate for storing batteries, roofing, chemical and constructional industries, as a protective covering in galvanized structural steel products, zinc oxides in rubber industry, production of sulphuric Thorite
7. Gold: international standard for monetary system and medium of exchange in trade; valued as an ornament and jewelry, dental appliances.
8. Silver: used for photographic film emulsions, plating, brazing, alloys, table ware and electronic equipment, coinage.
9. Uranium: curing of thyroid disorder and cancer; sterilization, production of nuclear energy, destroys cells causing anemia and induces mutation.
10. Monazite: source of thorite.
11. Thorite: source of atomic energy, manufacture of mantles for Candescent gas light.
12. Zircon: source of metallic zirconium used for nuclear reactor.
13. Limestone: for production of cement, liming material for to reduce soil acidity; fluxing agent in tin smelting.
14. Marble: for production of cement, liming material for to reduce soil acidity; production of local snuff.
15. Industrial rocks and gravels: ceramic materials, as building and construction materials.
16. Clay/Shale: Ceramic materials for production of INA ware, shale, sewery pipe, and sand are used in glass production.
17. Kaolin: making bricks, drain tile and sewery pipe; manufacture of China and pottery, filler in paper, rubber industry.
18. Feldspar: manufacture of porcelain, glass, as ornamental material.
19. Salt: Seasoning food and stain removing agent.
20. Topaz: Ornaments or jewelry
21. Coal: being high calorific material, it is used in driving trains, by chemical industries, in cooking.
22. Lignite: for domestic heating, generating thermal electricity and in chemical industry.

Nigerian Government and the Development of Creative Potentials

Section 1(8a-c) of Nigerian National Policy on Education (2008) provides that: "In order to fully realize the goals of education in Nigeria and gain from its contribution to the national economy, Government shall take necessary measures to ensure that:

- a. educational activities shall be learner centered for maximum self-development and self-fulfillment;

- b. teaching shall be practical, activity based, experimental and ICT supported;
- c. education shall be related to overall community needs..." Furthermore, section 1, subsections (9 and f) state that "the quality of instruction at all levels of education shall be oriented towards inculcating the following values: ...acquisition of competencies necessary for self reliance.

In the light of the above, Otache (2010:30) has pointed out numerous ways by which governments promote manpower training and utilization in Nigeria as follows:

- provision of short-term or soft loans through government agencies like National Directorate of Employment;
- organization of workshops and seminars where people are trained in trades such as carpentry, sewing, soap-making, shoe-making, poultry, fishery, etc;
- encouragement in the use of indigenous materials in industrial development activities (Local Contents Policy);
- fiscal and non-fiscal incentives for entrepreneurs and investors in the small-scale subsector of the economy in form of rebate on taxes paid as well as tax holidays;
- introduction of entrepreneurship development as a course to be offered in tertiary institutions in Nigeria;
- the institution of Entrepreneurship Promotion Award by the Central Bank of Nigeria: where the CBN recognizes the various categories of persons or institutions that have distinguished themselves in various facets of entrepreneurship development by giving them different categories of awards.

Furthermore, the Nigerian government has put in place several agencies that are saddled with manpower training and utilization in Nigeria; some of them are listed as follows:

National Directorate of Employment (NDE): Its roles are:

- a. To conduct vocational and apprenticeship training for the youths in the areas of Information and Communication Technology, textiles, catering, hair-dressing etc;
- b. To provide soft or short-term loans to young entrepreneurs to start small-scale businesses through selected commercial banks;
- c. To foster and promote self-employment;
- d. To recommend

Industrial Development Centre (IDC):

- a. To render both technical and managerial assistance to small-scale enterprises;
- b. To provide industrial extension services to small-scale enterprises;
- c. To train and develop small-scale entrepreneurs and managers;
- d. To assist in product planning, development and control;
- e. To advise on the viable projects to select;
- f. To assist in technical appraisal of loan application;
- g. To assist in product design and redesign.

Centre for Entrepreneurship and Development Research (CEDR):

- a. To develop entrepreneurship spirit and mindset among Nigerians especially school leavers;
- b. To facilitate and enhance job creation among unemployed and underemployed school leavers;
- c. To facilitate skill acquisition and development among Nigerians especially school leavers;
- d. To enhance business for small scale operators and artisans especially through capacity building and linkage to finance and facilitate rural development in Nigeria and engage in development research.

Centre for Industrial Research and Development (CIRD):

- a. To provide counseling, technical assistance and training in productivity improvement and organizational development;
- b. To disseminate information on investment opportunity, finance, input requirements for manufacturing of specific products
- c. To render extension services in starting and maintaining a business;
- d. To conduct managerial training, seminars and workshops in different areas of smallscale businesses;
- e. To render consulting services on feasibility studies, financial analysis, project monitoring and evaluation;
- f. To conduct researches into various aspects of industrial development in Nigeria.

Centre for Management Development (CMD): To train and develop manpower for small-scale enterprises;

- a. Providing consultancy services as well as research and technical information to smallscale industrialist;
- b. To design programmes that will stimulate entrepreneurship.

Polytechnics and Universities

Polytechnics and Universities also play vital roles in manpower training and development in

Nigeria. This is achieved by teaching business-related courses such as Business

Administration and Management, Marketing, Entrepreneurship Development, Accounting, Economics etc.

They also engage in consultancy services as well as serve as centres for seminars, workshops and conferences where prospective and existing small industrialists are trained and developed on how to effectively and efficiently manage their businesses. Nigerian Graduates and the challenge of joblessness

Quartz Africa (2016) has reported that “By some estimates Nigerian tertiary education institutions produce up to 500, 000 graduates every year and there are also Nigerian graduates who studied abroad who come home to compete for jobs” (Para. 1) The online tabloid also pointed out that “...employers have attributed the problem to the quality of unemployable as they lack required skills”; Stressing that Nigeria’s university system is mostly overpopulated which results to a situation whereby universities struggle to deliver quality education as available facilities are over stretched. This implies that for effective teaching and learning to take place, the ratio of students per teacher is paramount.

Consequently, Olatomide and Adesola (2015) have rightly noted that:

Currently Nigeria has a youth population of about 80 million which is about 60 percent of the population, more than 70 percent are said to be unemployed. They maintained that “The danger of unemployment and idleness are very prominent as majority of the youths are roaming about the streets in search of jobs in order to survive, where there is no job, some of the youth out of frustration take to vices like engaging in criminality and drug abuse. Challenges which plague the Nigerian youth and acts as factor militating against the full realization of their potentials, includes: lack of access to education, high rate of unemployment, extreme poverty, political and economic marginalization, exposure to conflict and food insecurity.

Furthermore, a recent report published by the National Bureau of Statistics (2018) reveals that: the category of unemployed persons comprised 8.5 million people who engage in an economic activity for at least an hour and 7.5 million people who did absolutely nothing. Also, 18.02 million people were underemployed, as they worked for 20 to 39 hours a week, which is less than the 40 hours required to be classified among the workforce. Fully employed persons, who worked for 40 hours and above in the third quarter of 2017, were 51.06 million people, resulting in a total of 77.6 million people engaged in an extent of economic activity (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

The Challenges of Creative Potential Development in Nigerian system of Education

1. Overdependence on paper qualification/certificate
2. Too much emphasis on theories and principles, rather than activity-based, practical and ICT supported method of teaching and learning;
3. Inadequate funding of the educational sector
4. Lack of technology/training equipment for processing of community based raw materials
5. Poor/lack of maintenance culture
6. Poor attitude to learning

Conclusion

No society can develop beyond the capacity of its human resources. Therefore, investment in training, skills acquisition and education must inform the perfection of work through better use of available resources and technology which ultimately, will enhance employability of school products, job creation, performance and productivity. The need for government to promote acquisition of indigenous knowledge and creative education in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized, as this will not only enhance job creation but will also boost the GDP of the nation as well as reduce the rate of unemployment, joblessness and criminality in the society.

Recommendations

1. Government should first of all guarantee safety of lives and property in Nigeria by beefing up the security architecture of the country.
2. Teaching and learning in school should be practical, activity-based, experimental and ICT supported, with little emphasis on theories and alien ideas or ideologies.
3. The equipment/technology required for practical learning and training in Nigerian schools should be adequately provided and maintained by government, likewise the professionals that would man the equipment.
4. Government should provide and maintain more infrastructures that will create the enabling environment for business and economic activities to thrive.
5. Education should promote indigenous knowledge and invention of relevant technology for dealing with the physical environment.

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